

**University of Belgrade
Faculty of Agriculture**

The 3rd International UNIFood Conference
UNIFood2024 Conference

Book of Abstracts

UNIFOOD

Belgrade, June 28-29, 2024.

UNIFood2024 Conference - Book of Abstract

The 3rd International UNIFood Conference – UNIFood2024

Publisher

University of Belgrade - Faculty of Agriculture
6 Nemanjina street
11080 Zemun - Belgrade

For Publisher

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University of Belgrade
Faculty of Agriculture

Editors

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Cover Design Layout, technical preparation, typesetting

Ivana Isaković

Print run

20 copies

Printing house

Faculty of Agriculture, Nemanjina 6, 11080 Belgrade

ISBN: 978-86-7834-438-1

Belgrade, 2024.

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UNIFood2024 Conference
28th-29th June 2024 University of Belgrade
3rd International UNIFood Conference

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

663/664(048)

INTERNATIONAL UNIFood Conference (3 ; 2024 ; Beograd)

Book of Abstracts : The 3rd International UNIFood Conference, UNIFood2024 Conference, Belgrade, June 28-29, 2024. / [editors Mirjana Pešić, Slađana Stanojević].
- Belgrade : University, Faculty of Agriculture, 2024 (Beograd : Faculty of Agriculture).
- 165 str. ; 30 cm

Tiraž 20.

ISBN 978-86-7834-438-1

a) Храна -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 147592713

ELEMENTAL PROFILES OF BERMET WINES AND ASSOCIATED HEALTH RISK

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Bermet is a sweet wine enriched with medicinal plants and spices, originally intended for medicinal purposes, but later produced as a regular dessert wine. It is a specialty of Fruška Gora wine region in northern Serbia. The importance of the wine elemental composition is multifaceted: certain chemical elements affect sensory properties, multi-element profiling could contribute to geographical origin differentiation and toxic elements have potential to endanger consumers' safety. The goal of the current study was to investigate elemental profiles and to assess health risk associated with Bermet wines. Elemental profiling (Be, B, Al, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Sr, Mo, Cd, Sn, Sb, Te, Ba, Hg, Tl, Pb) of 12 bottled Bermet wines was conducted by ICP-MS analysis. Health risk was estimated for men and women taking into account several wine consumption scenarios: population average, regular drinkers only and chronic heavy drinkers according to the World Health Organization, and the Serbian national food consumption survey data. The study revealed great differences in elements concentrations. However, all samples exhibited hazard indices well below 1, corresponding to the negligible non-carcinogenic risk. The minimum level of margin of exposure (MOE) associated with lead nephrotoxicity and with carcinogenic risk of arsenic exposure indicated no risk (74 and 9, respectively, in both cases for men drinking wine at volumes reported in the national consumption survey). On the other hand, lifetime cancer risk approach applied to arsenic showed that at the mean level of exposure the tolerable risk of 1 extra lifetime cancer case per 100,000 persons was slightly exceeded in heavy drinking and national wine consumption scenarios, for both men and women. Careful approach and monitoring of the influencing factors (endogenous sources, conditions of grape growth and winemakers' interventions) can contribute to the optimisation of the wine elemental composition.

Keywords: wine, food safety, public health, Fruška Gora